

Syntheses of some New Heterocycles from 4'-Aminochromones. Part-I

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Syntheses of some new pyrazoles from hitherto unknown 4'-aminochromones have been described. Their structures have been confirmed on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral data.

Flavonoids have been found to possess a number of physiological properties¹. The pyrazoles find their application in the fields of drugs², agriculture, analytical reagent and dyes³. It was thought that interesting results may be obtained by preparing compounds which contain both the flavone and the pyrazole moieties and the present work is directed towards the syntheses of a few such novel compounds.

The common method of preparing a pyrazole has been the condensation of a dicarbonyl compounds with hydrazine and its derivatives. In the present study 4'-hydrazinoflavone (7) was condensed with a number of 1,3-diketones to afford the desired pyrazoles. The compounds 10 were obtained by a series of reactions as shown in Scheme 1.

Recently, Fernandes and Counthino⁴ have prepared flavanopyrazole by the condensation of a flavanohydrazine with one aliphatic dicarbonyl compound. The present study therefore was undertaken not only to prepare a few hitherto unknown pyrazoles but also to examine the generality of the procedure using aromatic β -diketones.

The nitrochromone (4) was obtained in excellent yield starting with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (1) and *p*-nitrobenzoic acid via compounds 2 and 3 following the reported procedure⁵. The reduction of 4 to the aminochromone (6) was effected using sodium dithionite.

Compound 3 on refluxing with bromine in dioxan directly gave compound 5. The same compound could also be obtained by brominating 4 with CuBr_2 using ethyl acetate-chloroform as solvent. 5 could also be reduced to 6 by sodium dithionite. 6 was also been prepared using slightly different starting material (Scheme 2).

Compound 11 gave 12 which when reacted with glacial acetic acid and HCl furnished 13. The corresponding bromo compounds 14 could be obtained from the β -diketone (12) using bromine in dioxan as well as by direct bromination of the chromone (13) using CuBr_2 in ethyl acetate-chloroform mixture.

The over all yield of the amino compound by the procedure adopted in Scheme 1 is much better than the procedure adopted in Scheme 2.

The diazo compounds (6a-d) were used in solution without isolating them and on reduction the hydrazines (8) were thrown out from the solution as deep brownish red solid in almost quantitative yield. Finally, the hydrazines in acetic acid solution were condensed with the dibenzoylmethanes using catalytic amount of concentrated HCl. The yields of the flavanopyrazoles, generally obtained as crystalline product were 50-60%. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of elemental analysis and spectral data.

Experimental

The m.ps. were recorded in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer and the pmr on a EM-360 spectrometer.

2-(4'-Nitrobenzoyloxy)acetophenone (2)/2-(4'-acetamidobenzoyloxy)acetophenone (11): A mixture of *o*-hydroxyacetophenones (0.0065 mol) and *p*-nitrobenzoic acid/*p*-acetamidobenzoic acid (0.007 mol) dissolved in pyridine (5-10 ml) was treated with POCl_3 (0.03 ml) and stirred at 60-80°. The solid obtained on acidification was washed successively with 2% NaOH and water and crystallised from suitable solvent: 2a $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_5\text{Br}_2$ (80%), m.p. 185-86° (EtOH); 2b $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_5$ (75%), 172-73° (EtOH); 11a $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_4\text{Br}_2$ (45%), 145-47° (MeOH); 11b $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_4$ (42%), 131-32° (EtOAc).

2-Hydroxy- ω -(4'-nitrobenzoyl)acetophenone (3)/2-hydroxy- ω -(4'-acetamidobenzoyloxy)acetophenone (12): A mixture of the esters (2/11) (0.01 mol) in dry pyridine and solid KOH (0.03 mol) was stirred for 2 h at 60-80°, then cooled and decomposed with ice and sulphuric acid. The yellow precipitate of β -diketone thus obtained was washed with water and crystallised: 3a $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_5\text{Br}_2$ (80%), m.p. 226-27° (EtOAc); 3b $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_5$ (70%), m.p. 218-19° (EtOH); 12a $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_4\text{Br}$ (40%), m.p. 211-13° (EtOAc); 12b $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_4$ (50%), m.p. 198-99° (MeOH).

a; R=Br, R₁=R₂=R₄=H, R₃=Cl, R₅=CH₃ b; R=R₁=R₄=Br, R₂=H, R₃=Cl, R₅=CH₃
 c; R=R₁=R₂=R₄=H, R₃=Cl, R₅=CH₃ d; R=R₄=Br, R₁=R₂=H, R₃=Cl, R₅=CH₃
 e; R=R₁=R₂=R₄=Br, R₃=H

Scheme 1

2-(4'-Nitrophenyl)chromone (4)/2-(4'-acetamidophenyl)chromone (13): The β -diketone (3/12) was refluxed in glacial acetic acid for 2 h with catalytic amount of concentrated HCl. On working up, the solid obtained was crystallised from a suitable solvent: **4a** $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_7\text{NO}_4\text{Br}_2$ (90%), m.p. 293–94° (AcOH); **4b** $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_4$ (85%), m.p. 279–80° (AcOH); **13a** $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3\text{Br}_2$ (70%), m.p. 348–50° (AcOH); **13b** $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3$ (75%), m.p. 310–11° (EtOAc).

3-Bromo-2-(4'-nitrophenyl)chromone (5)/3-bromo-2-(4'-acetamidophenyl)chromone (14): 2-Hydroxydibenzoylmethane (0.001 mol) was dissolved in anhydrous dioxan (5 ml) and bromine (0.05 ml) was added to it at room temperature with stirring till the colour of bromine completely disappeared. On working up it gave the 3-bromoflavone, which was crystallised from a suitable solvent: **5a** $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_4\text{Br}_2$ (70%), m.p. 280–81° (AcOH); **5b** $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_4\text{Br}$ (68%), m.p. 260–61° (AcOH); **14a** $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_8\text{NO}_3\text{Br}_2$ (70%), m.p. 318–20° (AcOH); **14b** $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{10}\text{NO}_3\text{Br}$ (60%), m.p. 297–98° (pyridine).

The same 3-bromoflavanes were also prepared by an alternative route. The chromone 4/13 was dissolved in ethyl acetate-chloroform mixture (2 : 1) and CuBr_2 was then added to the refluxing solution.

The mixture was refluxed till the grey precipitate of Cu_2Br_2 did not separate. On working up, it gave the bromo compound. The compounds obtained were identical in all respect with the corresponding compounds prepared by the first method.

2-(4'-Aminophenyl)chromone (6) from 5 and 4: To a suspension of the flavone (5, 4) in refluxing ethanol-water (2 : 1), powdered sodium dithionite was added in instalments and refluxing continued till the colour of the solution changed to orange. The solution was then filtered hot and on work up light brown crystals were obtained which were crystallised from suitable solvent: **a** $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3\text{Br}_2$ (60%), m.p. 268–69° (pyridine); ν_{max} 3 350 (ArNH_2), 1 620 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1 240 cm^{-1} ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$); **b** $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{NO}_3\text{Br}$ (60%), m.p. 233–36° (pyridine); ν_{max} 3 345 (ArNH_2), 1 620 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1 230 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$) cm^{-1} ; δ 7.1–8.3 (8H, m, ArH), 4.12 (s, NH_2 proton as hump); **c** $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_3$ (80%), m.p. 240–41° (MeOH); **d** $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{NO}_3\text{Br}_2$ (75%), m.p. 293–94° (DMF); ν_{max} 3 345 (ArNH_2), 1 630 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$), 1 245 ($\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C}$) cm^{-1} .

Aminoflavone (6) from 13 and 14: The hydrolysis of 2-(4'-acetamido)chromones (13, 14) was done by refluxing with H_2SO_4 (1 : 1) for 1 h. It was then cooled and poured into water, yield 50%. The amino-

flavones obtained by this procedure showed identical m.p., m.m.p. and gave superimposable ir spectra.

4-Hydrazinoflavones (8): The aminoflavone (1.5 g) dissolved in HCl solution (5%, 50 ml) was diazotised at 0–5° by adding NaNO₂ solution (5%; 10 ml) and the mixture stirred for 30 min maintaining the same temperature. The clear solution was then slowly added with stirring to ice-cold aqueous Na₂SO₃ (5 g, 50 ml). Stirring was continued for another 2 h allowing the mixture to attain room temperature. The mixture was then neutralised with cold HCl (2 N), when a brown coloured solid was precipitated, which was directly used for the next stage. The hydrazines decomposed on heating and did not give a sharp m.p.

Pyrazoles (10a–e): To a refluxing solution of 8 (0.01 mol) and a β-diketone (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid, a trace of concentrated HCl was added and refluxing continued for another 2 h. The solid obtained after cooling and pouring into cold water, was washed with dilute HCl and water, and crystallised from suitable solvent: a C₃₁H₁₉O₃Br₂Cl₂N₂ (56%), m.p. 199–200° (pyridine); ν_{max} 1 645 (C=O), 1 350 (C–O–C), 1 550 (γ-pyrone ring), 1 605 cm⁻¹ (>C=N of pyrazole), δ 6.75 (1H, s, proton on C-3 of chromone ring), 2.44 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.26 (1H, s, proton on C-4 of pyrazole ring), hydroxyl proton merged with aromatic proton, 7.4–8.0 (14H, m); b C₃₁H₁₇O₃ClBr₄N₂ (55%), m.p. 209–10° (EtOH–CHCl₃); c C₃₁H₂₁O₃ClN₂ (55%), m.p. 198–99° (EtOH–CHCl₃); d C₃₁H₁₈O₃ClBr₂N₂ (50%), m.p. 180–83° (EtOH), ν_{max} 1 605

(C=N of pyrazole), 1 640 (C=O), 1 550, 1 450 (γ-pyrone ring), 1 350 cm⁻¹ (C–O–C); e C₃₀H₁₄O₃Br₆N₂ (53%), m.p. 135–38° (EtOH); δ 6.6 (1H, s, proton on C-3 of chromone ring), 7.10 (1H, s, on C-4 of pyrazole ring). Hydroxyl proton merged with aromatic proton, 7.0–8.2 (12H, m, ArH).

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